

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Open-access content for CSA-Platform

Deliverable 6.9

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
KER	Key Exploitable Result
RLA	Regional and Local Authority

PROJECT PARTNERS

No	Participant organisation English name	Acronym	Country
1	University of Antwerp	UA	Belgium
2	Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change	CMCC	Italy
3	ACTIERRA	ACTIERRA	France
4	E3-Modelling	E3M	Greece
5	Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research	PIK	Germany
6	Verhaert New Products and Services nv	VERHAERT	Belgium
7	Fundación Empresa – Universidad Gallega	FEUGA	Spain
8	National Centre for Scientific Research “Demokritos”	NCSR	Greece
9	Czech University of Life Sciences Prague	CZU	Czech Republic
10	LUT University	LUT	Finland
11	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	NTNU	Norway
12	University of Vigo	UVIGO	Spain
13	Epsilon Malta Ltd	EPSILON	Malta
14	French Ecological Transition National Agency	ADEME	France
15	Westcountry Rivers Trust	WRT	United Kingdom
16	Mediterranean Sea and Coast	MEDSEA	Italy
17	CETMAR	CETMAR	Spain
18	City of Lappeenranta	LAPP	Finland
19	Municipality of Egaleo	MOE	Greece
20	Water Europe	WE	Belgium
21	Euroquality	EQY	France
22	Gjøvik municipality	MOG	Norway

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents TransformAr's online legacy strategy, with key information on where to find the project's 13 Key Exploitable Results. Five main online platforms gather these results, namely MIP4ADAPT, Climate-ADAPT, the Climate Innovation Window, the Horizon Results Platform, the Green Deal Support Office webpage, Zenodo and the TransformAr project website.

Adding to this mapping, this documents provides direct links to the Key Exploitable Results for the reader to easily access them directly.

1. Context

As one of the first Mission Adaptation projects, TransformAr worked with the sister projects [ARSINOE](#) and [CLIMATE IMPETUS](#), *i.e.*, funded under the same call topic LC-GD-1-3-2020 - Climate-resilient Innovation Packages for EU regions, and the linked Coordination and Support Action (CSA) [REGILIENCE](#) to refine on which online platforms Key Exploitable Results (KERs) could be shared for the project's legacy.

After REGILIENCE's review of potential online platforms which could be used ([link](#) to final platforms showcased by REGILIENCE), and in line with the development of the MIP4ADAPT platform by the Mission Adaptation to Climate Change, TransformAr partners identified both (i) 13 Key Exploitable Results that should be widely shared and (ii) seven online platforms to support this effort for KERs' online legacy and replication.

2. Key Exploitable Results

Based on the project's final exploitation plan (D6.7), support from the Horizon Results Booster service, compilation and optimization activities done by the coordinator in T6.3 (D6.3 and D6.5) and on main priorities discussed with TransformAr partners, the following KERs list was established to be put on online platforms during the last year of the project:

- **TransformAr Playbook** – regions and local authorities
- **Data visualisation platform** - regions and local authorities
- **6 Adaptation stories** - regions and local authorities
- **2 Green Deal Success Stories** - regions and local authorities
- **Three Policy Briefs on Transformational Adaptation, Monitoring and Stakeholder engagement** – policy makers
- **A Replication guide** – regions and local authorities
- **A Replicability assessment tool** – solution providers
- **An online Scorecard for Transformational Adaptation** - regions and local authorities
- **6 Best practices on Stakeholder management and on Change management** - regions and local authorities
- **Sustainability profiles of solutions** – solution providers
- **20 local adaptation solutions** – solution providers and regions and local authorities

This list of KERs is also presented in Figure 1 below, presented per main target end-user groups.

KERs for Regional and Local Authorities

TransformAr Playbook

Data visualisation platform

Adaptation stories, Green Deal Success Stories

Replication Guide

Scorecard for Transformational Adaptation

Best practices on climate adaptation

20 local adaptation solutions tested locally

KERs for Adaptation Solution Providers

KERs for Policy Makers

Figure 1. TransformAr KERs per end-user category

3. Online legacy strategy

Project partners have made KERs presented in Section 2 available in open-access on seven online platforms. The platforms selected have been chosen based on (i) KERs’ target end-user groups, (ii)

 Climate Innovation Window Platform manager: BRIGAD Connect End-users: Solution providers, RLAs Platform time frame: /		
 Horizon Results Platform Platform manager: EC End-users: All profiles Platform time frame: /		
 TransformAr website Platform manager: Water Europe End-users: All profiles Platform time frame: maintained until 2033		

platforms’ objectives, outreach and end-users and (iii) KERs’ format compatibility with the platforms. This selection and decision process for TransformAr’s online legacy strategy is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Overview of platforms selected for TransformAr’s online legacy

Project partners have also worked on different formats and documents that could support the online legacy of specific KERs, with for instance the example of the Nature-Based local adaption solutions – presented in Annex 1, which also have a supporting explanatory video – see Annex 2.

3.1 MIP4ADAPT

As presented on the REGILIENCE website, “MIP4Adapt supports European regional and local authorities to prepare and plan their adaptation pathways to climate resilience. MIP4Adapt is facilitating a Community of Practice and delivering technical assistance to enable regions and local authorities to e.g. use their existing climate vulnerability and risk assessments to develop climate adaptation plans and fund and implement climate adaptation solutions and many more.”¹

KERs from TransformAr that are accessible on the MIP4ADAPT platform (direct [link](#)) are the following:

- **TransformAr Playbook** – direct [link](#)
- **Six Adaptation Stories:**
 - The Resilience Index: Assessing Aquaculture’s Adaptive Capacity for Informed Decision-Making – direct [link](#)
 - Coastal Contract: A Governance Approach for Integrated Wetland Management – direct [link](#)
 - Redirecting local funding lines to climate change adaptation in a European outermost region – direct [link](#)
 - Citizens’ willingness to act on stormwater management – direct [link](#)
 - Improving climate awareness among Greek students – direct [link](#)
 - The Bankability of Nature-based Solutions in Devon and Cornwall – direct link soon available
- **Policy Brief of Transformational Adaptation** – direct [link](#)
- **Policy Brief on Monitoring** – direct [link](#)

TransformAr partners are also exploring which KERs will be shared on the Mission Adaptation Community of Practice platform Futurium.

3.2 Climate-ADAPT

Still from the REGILIENCE website², “Climate-ADAPT aims to support Europe in adapting to climate change helping users to access and share data and information on: expected climate change in Europe, current and future vulnerability of regions and sectors, EU, national and transnational adaptation strategies and actions and many more.”

KERs from TransformAr that are accessible on the Climate-ADAPT platform (direct [link](#)) are the following:

- **Data visualisation platform** – direct [link](#)
- **Replication Guide** – direct [link](#)
- **Replicability assessment tool** – direct [link](#)
- **Scorecard for Transformational Adaptation** – direct [link](#)
- **6 Best practices on Stakeholder management and on Change management** - direct [link](#)

¹ Accessed on 23/09/2025 via <https://regilience.eu/cooperation-platforms>

² Ibid

3.3 Climate Innovation Window

“Climate Innovation Window platform is dedicated to innovations that can tackle climate change challenges. This a place, where climate adaptation innovators, end-users, and investors can connect and meet each other’s needs.”³

KERs from TransformAr that are accessible on the Climate Innovation Window (direct [link](#)) are the following:

- **20 local adaptation solutions**
 - Discrete Choice Experiment on Willingness to Pay – direct [link](#)
 - Stormwater Monitoring – direct [link](#)
 - Biofiltration Area for Urban Runoff – direct [link](#)
 - Guadeloupe Local Adaptation Fund – direct [link](#)
 - Nudging solution – direct [link](#)
 - Mussel raft monitoring – direct [link](#)
 - Intertidal monitoring solution – direct [link](#)
 - Resilience Index – direct [link](#)
 - Citizen application (Lappeenranta) – direct [link](#)
 - Climate Innovation Hub – direct [link](#)
 - Awareness raising modules – direct [link](#)
 - Smart Gate – direct [link](#)
 - Coastal contracts – direct [link](#)
 - Nature-Based Solutions in Westcountry – direct link soon available
 - Citizen application - direct link soon available
 - Demand analysis for social services and infrastructures - direct link soon available
 - Smart Climate Stations - direct link soon available
 - Payment for ecosystem services - direct link soon available
 - Citizen application (Gjovik) - direct link soon available
 - Insurance schemes – not uploaded on the Climate Innovation Window

3.4 Horizon Results Platform

The Horizon Results Platform gathers main results and knowledge created in Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 project.

KERs from TransformAr that are accessible on the Horizon Results Platform (direct [link](#)) are the following:

- **TransformAr Playbook** – direct [link](#)
- **Policy Brief of Transformational Adaptation** – direct [link](#)
- **Policy Brief on Monitoring** – direct [link](#)
- **Policy Brief on Stakeholder engagement** – direct [link](#)
- **Replication Guide** – direct link soon available
- **Replicability assessment tool** – direct [link](#)
- **Scorecard for Transformational Adaptation** – direct [link](#)
- **Sustainability profiles of solutions** – direct [link](#)
- **Data visualisation platform** – direct link soon available

³ Ibid

- **6 Best practices on Stakeholder management and on Change management** – direct link soon available

3.5 Green Deal Support Office website

The Green Deal Support Office website gathers results and knowledge created in the Green Deal projects that were funded in 2021. The European Green Deal projects develop solutions that respond to the climate crisis, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, provide more protection to Europe's biodiversity and habitats under threat, and accelerate a sustainable socio-economic recovery, leaving no one behind.

Only Green Deal Success Stories are available on the Green Deal Support Office website (direct [link](#)). The direct links to the two TransformAr success stories are provided below:

- Empowering communities for climate resilience: Gjøvik's flood detection innovation – direct [link](#);
- Innovative governance tool to manage and protect wetlands – direct [link](#).

3.6 Zenodo

All public KERs which are public deliverables of TransformAr, including open-access academic publications, are available on Zenodo. All can be accessed using this direct [link](#) to the TransformAr Zenodo community.

3.7 TransformAr website

All KERs presented in Section 2 of this document are also available on the TransformAr project website, on a dedicated Results page (direct [link](#)), as shown on Figure 3 . On this page of the website, all KERs, public deliverables and also additional resources (*e.g.*, summary sheets on complex deliverables, link to videos and factsheets) are organised per step of the Regional Adaptation Support Tool. This is to facilitate KERs' access to end-users who would like to follow this approach supported by the Mission Adaptation to Climate Change.

The website will be maintained until 2033 by Water Europe.

TransformAr results per RAST step

<p>STEP 1</p> <p>Preparing the ground for adaptation</p> <p>More info</p>		
<p>STEP 4</p> <p>Assessing and selecting adaptation options</p> <p>More info</p>		
<p>TransformAr Transversal Solutions</p> <p>More info</p>		

Figure 3. TransformAr website – Results landing webpage

ANNEX 1. Nature-based solutions presented on platforms

CLIMATE INNOVATION WINDOW European Climate Resilience Innovation Platform Powered by BRG&G Connect

Invest: € 8, 6 | Filters | Issues | Areas | Solutions | About us | Benefits | Services

COASTAL FLOODS | DROUGHTS | RIVER FLOODS | BIODIVERSITY | MARINE AND FISHERIES
ENGINEERING AND BUILT ENVIRONMENT | MODELS AND TOOLS | TECHNOLOGY

Smart Gate

Intelligent and remote-controlled sluice gate that opens automatically based on real-time data, enabling adaptive water flow regulation. Designed to protect ecosystems and support local fisheries, it enhances both environmental and economic resilience

- ✓ Climate adaptation
- ✓ Water management
- ✓ Biodiversity conservation

By MEDSEA Foundation

The innovation addresses poor water circulation, flooding, and ecological degradation in coastal wetlands. Without proper flow management, wetlands face anoxia, sedimentation, and biodiversity loss, especially under increasing climate

CLIMATE INNOVATION WINDOW European Climate Resilience Innovation Platform Powered by BRG&G Connect

Business | Market | Invest: € 7, 3 | Filters | Issues | Areas | Solutions | About us | Benefits | Services

HEAVY PRECIPITATION | PLUVIAL FLOODS | BIODIVERSITY | URBAN AREAS | WATER MANAGEMENT
ENGINEERING AND BUILT ENVIRONMENT | NATURE-BASED SERVICES | TECHNOLOGY

Biofiltration Area for Urban Runoff

New integrative biofiltration area in the city centre as part of new urban adaptation standards, to reduce the amount of water led to storm water sewer systems, to filter harmful substances, and to filter stormwater into groundwater.

- ✓ Improved lake water quality
- ✓ Decreased urban flooding
- ✓ Improved urban biodiversity

There is an increasing demand for decentralized stormwater management solutions driven by urbanization, stricter environmental regulations, and public interest in sustainable practices. This demand is particularly notable in urban areas facing challenges from impervious surfaces and rising pollution levels. The a biofiltration area focuses on efforts to address the municipal environment and urban challenges due

ANNEX 3. Nature-based solutions explanatory videos

Inside Lappeenranta's Climate Plan: Smart Solutions for Stormwater & Flooding | TransformAr Project

Inside the West Country's Plan to Combat Flooding & Pollution | TransformAr Project

Saving a Paradise: How a Smart Gate is Rescuing Sardinia's Coastal Wetlands

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

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